

4th International Conference on Computing and Information Technology Trends (CCITT 2025)

January 23 ~ 24, 2025, Virtual Conference

<https://ccitt2025.org/index>

Scope & Topics

4th International Conference on Computing and Information Technology Trends (CCITT 2025) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Computing and Information Technology Trends. The Conference looks for significant contributions to all major fields of the Computer Science, Compute Engineering, Information Technology and Trends in theoretical and practical aspects.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to these topics only.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Business Intelligence
- Computer Architecture and Real Time Systems
- Computer Education
- Data Science
- Database and Data Mining
- Deep Learning
- Dependable, Reliable and Autonomic Computing
- Devops Models, Practices, Challenges
- Distributed and Parallel Systems
- DSP/Image Processing/Pattern Recognition/Multimedia
- E-Learning, E-Business, Enterprise Information Systems and E-Government
- Embedded System and Software
- Fuzzy Systems
- Game and Software Engineering
- Grid and Scalable Computing
- Information Technology Management
- Intelligent Information and Database Systems
- Internet of Things
- Knowledge Management
- Machine Learning & Applications
- Mobile and Ubiquitous Computing
- Modeling and Simulation
- Multimedia Systems and Services
- Natural Language Processing & Text Mining
- Networking and Communications
- Ontology and Semantic Web
- Performance Evaluation
- Security and Information Assurance
- Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) in the real World
- Smart cities
- Software Automation, Software as a Service (Saas)
- Software Engineering

- Swarm Intelligence
- Theoretical Computer Science
- Web and Internet Computing

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **November 23, 2024**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [International Journal on Cybernetics & Informatics \(IJCI\)](#) (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **CCITT 2025**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services \(IJITCS\)](#)
- [International Journal on Computational Science & Applications \(IJCSA\)](#)
- [Advanced Computing: An International Journal \(ACIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Applications \(IJCSEA\)](#)
- [International Journal of Distributed and Parallel systems \(IJDPS\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : November 23, 2024**
- Authors Notification : December 14, 2024
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : December 21, 2024

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: ccitt@ccitt2025.org (or) ccittconf@yahoo.com

For other details: <https://ccitt2025.org/index>

Paper Submission Link: <https://ccitt2025.org/submission/index.php>